

TABLE—1

Compound	Yield(%)	Methods of identification.
Terpinolene	3.75	IR, Maleic anhydride adduct ² , Co-TLC & GLC
α -pinene	3.20	IR, NMR, Co-TLC & GLC
β -pinene	2.50	NMR, Nopinic acid, Co-TLC & GLC
β -caryophyllene	4.20	IR, NMR, Co-TLC & GLC
Methyl eugenol	2.10	IR, Co-TLC & GLC
Thymol	41.80	IR, Colour reactions, Co-TLC & GLC
1, 8-Cineole	5.45	IR, Iodol addition comp., Co-TLC & GLC
Eugenol	4.40	IR, n_D^{25} (1.5414), Co-TLC & GLC
Carvacrol	13.25	IR, n_D^{25} (1.5234), Phenylurethane, Co-TLC & GLC
β -Phellanderene	1.90	IR, Co-TLC & GLC

All the melting points of derivatives were compared with the melting points given by Gunther³.

Acknowledgement

We are indebted to Prof. H. Wagner, Director, Institut für Pharmazeutische Arzneimittellehre, Munchen (W. Germany) for IR, NMR and GLC. Thanks are also due to UGC for sanctioning the research project to one of us (R.K.B.) under which this work could be done.

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Chemical Examination of Essential Oil from the leaves of *Tagetes-erecta* Linn.

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PLANT: *Tagetes-erecta* Linn. (Family Compositae).
Procedure—Steam distillation (Yield 0.3%)
Physical Constants—Sp. gravity 0.8936, n_D^{25} 1.6147,

$[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2.436$, Acid value 1.4784, Ester value 30.68, Ester value after acetylation 142.35 and carbonyl value as $C_{10}H_{16}O$ 12.94%. *Previous work*: Few workers^{1,2} have reported the chemistry of essential oil from flowering tops and separated phenolic and non-phenolic terpenes of the oil.

The completely characterised constituents of the oil are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	Yield(%)	Methods of identification
δ -limonene	19.67	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4746, Co-TLC and GLC
α -pinene	1.36	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4662, Co-TLC and GLC
β -pinene	0.89	IR, Nopinic acid ³ , Co-TLC and GLC
Dipentene	0.67	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Ocimene	7.61	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4857, Co-TLC and GLC
β -phellandrene	4.97	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Linalool	26.80	IR, n_D^{25} 1.4624, Co-TLC and GLC
Geraniol	0.86	IR, NMR, Co-TLC and GLC
Menthol	0.93	IR, Co-TLC and GLC
Tagetone	13.39	IR, Methyl-isobutyl Ketone adduct ⁴ , Co-TLC and GLC
Nonanal	1.34	IR, NMR, Co-TLC and GLC
Linalylacetate	3.56	IR, n_D^{25} 1.6327, Co-TLC and GLC

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